

European Policy Brief

Policies Supporting Equity and Diversity in Teacher Education

Equity and Diversity in Teacher Education: Advancing the Professional Development of Teacher Educators in Europe

SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This policy brief presents the main policy messages emerging from the knowledge production and dissemination activities carried out in the Erasmus+ project “Equity and Diversity in Teacher Educator Professional Development” (ED-TED / 023-1-DE01-KA220-HED-000152242) at European, national, and institutional levels. The messages highlight four key recommendations to strengthen teacher educators’ professional development and enhance teacher education with a clear focus on equity and diversity:

At the European level:

- Establish a European network on Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (DEI) in teacher education. Facilitate shared knowledge production, transfer, and networking for teacher educators via initiatives like InFo-TED (International Forum on Teacher Educator Development)¹, including internationally shared resources like the ED-TED resource bank that are designed to improve DEI practices.

At the European and national levels:

- Build an infrastructure for teacher educators' collaborative learning and fund research to improve DEI practices across Europe. Support and sustain professional organisations such as VELON and VELOV (see Appendix 1) that provide professional development to teacher educators through collaborative learning and research.
- Consult teacher educators' professional organisations when designing DEI-related teacher education policies.

At the European, national and institutional levels:

- Adopt the realisation of DEI as a quality indicator in teacher education programmes. Ensure DEI is coherently integrated into programme content and teaching methods.
- Adopt teacher educators’ professional development in DEI as a quality indicator in teacher education programmes in higher education (see Figure 1). Promote collaborative teamwork to strengthen DEI knowledge, skills, and practices.

¹ <https://info-ted.eu>

Figure 1. Policy recommendations for teacher educator professional development in DEI.

INTRODUCTION

Inclusive and equitable education for all is one of the main goals the UN set for 2030 (UN, 2015). Teacher education for diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) is a key element therein. However, individual teacher educators often feel underprepared and are therefore uninvolved and overwhelmed regarding DEI education (Florian & Camedda, 2020; Guðjónsdóttir & Óskarsdóttir, 2020). Hence, there is a need to develop a universal and holistic framework for teacher education institutions on effective DEI curricula.

ED-TED is an Erasmus+ funded project, involving eight higher education institutions from seven European countries and three national organisations (see appendix 1). ED-TED promotes EU priorities on equity and diversity in education, contributing to Sustainable Development Goals 4 (quality education), 10 (reduced inequalities), and 17 (partnerships for the goals), while recognising the need for context-sensitive implementation informed by national and cultural factors. It aims to improve teacher education for DEI through three interconnected courses of action:

- (1) Mapping current practices, programmes, and policies in teaching for DEI to identify DEI related professional development needs of teacher educators (see the method section below).
- (2) Supporting teacher educators' professional development in DEI matters through an online, open access resource bank. The resource bank enables teacher educators to share their successful practices and facilitates networking and transformative learning through its virtual chat space (<https://info-ted.eu/resources/>)
- (3) Suggesting policies that would support individual as well as institutional professionalisation in educating for diversity and inclusion.

METHODS

The project team applied a systematic methodology to map policies and 'lived' practices in seven European countries at three levels: macro (national and regional policies), meso (teacher education institutions and programmes), and micro (individual practices). This

involved document analysis of the past ten years of national and institutional policies, and focus group interviews with student teachers, programme leaders, and teacher educators. The findings were validated through seven national webinars and one cross-national webinar that were held between March 2024 and May 2025, bringing together over 200 participants (including teacher educators, school principals, teachers, programme leaders, researchers, policymakers, teacher education associations and other stakeholders). In addition, the results were presented at European conferences (e.g. ECER 2024, ISATT 2025, NERA 2025). Findings were presented in two narratives per country²: one assessing diversity and inclusion policies, and the other describing provisions for student teachers and teacher educators' professionalisation in offering high quality education to all students.

MAIN FINDINGS

The main findings of our comprehensive mapping exercise are:

- The goal of providing high quality DEI responsive education is prevalent in policy documents of countries and teacher education institutions. However, there is a need for clear guidelines that would translate the general good intentions of local policies into practice.
- Too many teacher education programmes which have been analysed do not address diversity, equity and inclusion, or do so on a voluntary basis and/or as fragmented, add-on courses, rather than coherently integrating DEI into the programmes' content and teaching methods.
- Teacher educators need to acquire more knowledge and skills in DEI, preferably in collaboration with their colleagues.

The ED-TED findings underscore the need for a more coherent and multi-level policy approach to equity and diversity in teacher education. At the European level, strong policy commitments often lack operational clarity and alignment with national education systems and structures. At the national and institutional levels, programmes frequently struggle to integrate equity and diversity meaningfully into curricula and to provide professional development tailored to the specific needs of teacher educators. While individual teacher educators show a strong

² For more information and access to the narratives, see: <https://info-ted.eu/resources/?search=&researchtag=&mediatag=narratives>.

commitment to inclusive practices, challenges such as limited diversity within the teaching workforce and inconsistent collaboration with schools persist.

POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

General implications

The lack of shared and precise definitions of DEI across European teacher education contexts leads to fragmented understandings and inconsistent implementation in teacher education policies and practices. Policy frameworks should therefore promote the development of clear, commonly agreed definitions and measurable indicators, while allowing sufficient flexibility for national and institutional contexts to ensure coherence without undermining local relevance. As a key reference point for this endeavour, UNESCO defines DEI in higher education as "principles and practices that ensure equitable and supportive learning environments that respect, value, and respond to the differences among learners, ensuring that all higher education students regardless of background, identity or ability can participate and achieve their full potential through education"³. Furthermore, it is important to consider the diversity among teacher educators. Differences across national and institutional contexts highlight the flexibility of teacher education policies but also point to the need for stronger European coordination and shared reference frameworks for equity and diversity. Furthermore, teacher educators' limited involvement in policy design constrains the relevance and effectiveness of equity and diversity-related reforms, reducing opportunities for meaningful knowledge transfer between policy and practice.

Recommendations for policy makers and teacher education researchers at (inter)national level:

- Establish a European teacher education network on equity and diversity to facilitate shared knowledge production, transfer, and networking for teacher educators via organisations like VELON and VELOV, and initiatives like InFo-TED.

³ <https://www.unesco.org/en/query-list/d/diversity-and-inclusion-higher-education>

- Consult teacher educators' professional organizations when designing DEI-related teacher education policies.

Teacher education programmes

The limited integration of DEI in teacher education programmes risks reinforcing existing norms and practices, thereby reproducing inequalities for pre-service teachers and their future students. Without systematic embedding, equity and diversity remain peripheral rather than integral to programme design and pedagogical practice. For instance, Norway embeds equity and diversity explicitly in national strategy documents and institutional guidelines for teacher education, ensuring alignment with programme objectives.

Recommendation for programme leaders and teacher educators at institutional level:

- Adopt DEI as a quality indicator in teacher education programmes. These aspects should be considered: (a) Ensure DEI is coherently integrated into programme content and teaching methods, (b) enable practical teaching experiences for preservice teachers in schools with different social, cultural and language contexts, (c) establish diversity-responsive (course) evaluation as an integral part of teacher education programmes to enable productive feedback between teacher educators and students.

Teacher educators' professional development in DEI

An emphasis on individual professional development without sustained institutional support risks fragmented and uneven implementation of DEI principles and may overburden teacher educators. Some structured initiatives provide positive examples of collaborative, context-specific support: Norway's BalanseHub⁴ offers mentoring and peer learning opportunities for teacher educators, Finland's equity work groups facilitate cross-institutional collaboration on inclusive practices, and Ireland's Ubuntu and SCoTENS⁵ networks support international exchange and the development of inclusive teaching modules. In the Netherlands the

⁴ For more information, see: <https://balansehub.nifu.no/>

⁵ For more information, see: <https://scotens.org/about/>

sustained professional learning of teacher educators is supported by the registration trajectory for teacher educators.⁶

Current approaches to the professional development of teacher educators often emphasise generic teaching skills rather than targeted equity and diversity competencies, aligning more with a 'technical skills' understanding than a humanistic, socially conscious perspective. Targeted approaches include Germany's Annelie-Wellensiek-Center⁷, which provides participatory DEI workshops and research support for teacher educators by a diverse team. Similarly, Portugal integrates inclusive practices directly into teacher education programmes⁸, enabling pre-service teachers to engage with equity-focused pedagogy from the start.

Recommendations for policy makers, programme leaders and teacher educators at institutional level:

- Adopt teacher educators' professional development in DEI as a quality indicator in teacher education programmes. These aspects should be considered: (a) Provide mandatory and extensive modules on e.g. inclusive pedagogy, culturally sensitive teaching, and anti-discrimination, (b) promote diversity in teacher educators and university staff with regard to the representation of different ethnic, cultural, and socioeconomic backgrounds, gender and/or dis/ability (c) enable reflection on implicit biases and promote a positive attitude towards cultural and social diversity.
- Promote collaborative teamwork to strengthen DEI knowledge, skills, and practices. This implies a close collaboration across institutions and stakeholders, such as teacher educators, heads of departments of teacher education institutes, heads of schools, teacher unions, and policy makers at (inter)national levels. It also includes (a) a close policy dialogue between policy makers, teacher educators and teacher education researchers (both at national and European levels) and (b) local cooperations between schools and universities that understand student teachers' professional development as a shared responsibility.

⁶ For more information see: De Vries et al. (2025) | <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2025.2571916>

⁷ For more information see: <https://info-ted.eu/research/a-new-path-towards-inclusion-in-higher-education/>

⁸ For more information, see <https://info-ted.eu/research/a-narrative-of-provision-for-equity-and-diversity-in-portuguese-teacher-education/>

Infrastructure for teacher educators' professional development

Sustainable investment in collaborative infrastructures, such as VELON and VELOV organisations, and initiatives like InFo-TED (including the ED-TED resource bank), is essential to support long-term professionalisation through shared learning, knowledge transfer, and research.

Recommendation for policy makers and teacher education researchers at (inter)national level:

- Fund research to improve current DEI practices across Europe and encourage countries to build an infrastructure for teacher educators' professional development. This research should focus on (longitudinal) studies of the competency development of teacher educators as well as their beliefs and attitudes towards DEI. It should also actively involve people of marginalised groups in the research.

These implications and recommendations from the ED_TED project are evidence-informed impulses to support DEI policy and practices. Strengthening equity and diversity in teacher education requires long-term policy commitment, collaboration, sustained research investment, and institutional support to translate professional development into durable educational change.

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Appendix 1

PROJECT IDENTITY

PROJECT NAME:	Equity and Diversity in Teacher Education (ED-TED)
CONSORTIUM:	<p>University of Education Freiburg, Germany (Coordinator)</p> <p>Universidade do Minho, Portugal</p> <p>University of Ghent, Belgium</p> <p>KU Leuven, Belgium</p> <p>Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Norway</p> <p>Radboud University, the Netherlands</p> <p>University of Limerick, Ireland</p> <p>The University of Helsinki, Finland</p> <p>Associated Partners:</p> <p>The Dutch Teacher Educators Associations (VELON), the Netherlands¹</p> <p>Ubuntu Network, Ireland²</p> <p>Zentrum für Schulqualität und Lehrerbildung Baden-Württemberg (ZSL), Germany³</p>

¹ VELON – the Dutch Association for Teacher Educators – has, since 1975, supported teacher trainers in the Netherlands through professionalisation, networking, and advocacy, offering events, publications, and a national network to foster collaboration and growth, while ensuring their interests are represented in key decision-making processes. For more information, see <https://velon.nl/>

VELOV – The Association of Teacher Educators Flanders - aims to support teacher trainers at colleges and universities, as well as anyone else involved in the training, guidance, and professional development of (prospective) teachers. For more information, see <https://www.velov.be/>

² The Ubuntu Network is a community of post-primary initial teacher educators supporting Global Citizenship Education (GCE), fostering understanding of global development issues and equipping educators with the skills to integrate them into teaching for positive impact. In their value-based approach, they emphasise participation, dialogue, reflection, which are key for sustainable diversity-sensitive and human rights-based professional development. For more information, see <https://ubuntu.ie/>

³ Das Zentrum für Schulqualität und Lehrerbildung (ZSL) provides a research-based, centrally coordinated system focused on teaching quality for general and vocational schools in Baden-Württemberg. It links and strengthens teacher training and professional development through personnel and leadership training, curriculum and textbook approval, pedagogical and subject-specific programmes, classroom-related support, international cooperation, and a range of advisory services covering areas such as school career guidance, vocational orientation, special needs and talents, school psychology, prevention, and quality development. For more information, see <https://zsl-bw.de/Len/startpage>

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